

RESEARCH ARTICLE | MARCH 10 2025

Development of Co-rich glass-coated microwires with high GMI effect

Special Collection: [16th Joint MMM-Intermag Conference](#)A. Gonzalez

Articles You May Be Interested In

Single domain wall propagation in Co-rich magnetic microwires with graded magnetic anisotropy

AIP Advances (March 2025)

Effect of Joule heating on GMI and magnetic properties of Fe-rich glass-coated microwires

AIP Advances (March 2022)

Domain wall propagation in Fe-rich magnetic microwires with graded magnetic anisotropy

AIP Advances (March 2022)

AIP Advances
Special Topics Now Online

[Learn More](#)

AIP Publishing

Development of Co-rich glass-coated microwires with high GMI effect

Cite as: AIP Advances 15, 035213 (2025); doi: 10.1063/9.0000884
 Submitted: 10 November 2024 • Accepted: 3 December 2024 •
 Published Online: 10 March 2025

A. Gonzalez,^{1,2} P. Corte-León,^{1,2,3,4,a)} V. Zhukova,^{1,2,3} J. M. Blanco,^{2,3} J. Olivera,⁵ and A. Zhukov^{1,2,3,6,a)}

AFFILIATIONS

¹ Department of Polymers and Advanced Materials: Physics, Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Basque Country, UPV/EHU, 20018 San Sebastian, Spain

² Department of Applied Physics I, Escuela de Ingeniería de Gipuzkoa EIG, University of Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Plaza Europa 1, 20018 San Sebastian, Spain

³ EHU Quantum Center, University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, San Sebastian, Spain

⁴ Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, 27 Charles Babbage Road, Cambridge CB3 0FS, United Kingdom

⁵ Instituto de Física, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad Autónoma de Santo Domingo, Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic

⁶ IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

Note: This paper was presented at the 16th Joint MMM-Intermag Conference.

a) Authors to whom correspondence should be addressed: paula.corte@ehu.es and arkadi.joukov@ehu.es. Tel.: 34-943018611. Fax: 34-943017130

ABSTRACT

We studied the Giant Magneto-Impedance (GMI) effect and magnetic properties of $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated magnetic microwires with two different diameters. Substantially different frequency dependence of GMI effect is observed in studied microwires. A remarkable GMI ratio improvement up to 735% is observed after annealing of thicker Co-rich microwire. The observed modification of magnetic properties and GMI ratio improvement are discussed considering the internal stresses relaxation and a change in the magnetostriction coefficient sign and values after annealing.

© 2025 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1063/9.0000884>

I. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous magnetic materials prepared using rapid melt quenching can present excellent magnetic softness together with good mechanical and corrosion properties.¹⁻⁴ Additionally, rapid melt quenching is relatively simple technique allowing fast preparation of either amorphous ribbons or wires.^{1,3-7}

In particular amorphous ribbons or wires can present rather unusual magnetic properties, such as magnetic bistability^{5,6} and/or giant magnetoimpedance, GMI, effect.^{6,8,9} While magnetic bistability was reported in specially annealed amorphous ribbons,¹⁰ it can be easily realized even in as-cast amorphous wires.^{5,6} Additionally, the highest GMI effect is reported for amorphous magnetic wires.^{11,12} Thus, several publications GMI ratio above 600% have been reported for Co-rich amorphous wires.^{11,12}

Therefore, amorphous wires are intensively studied starting from the 70s.^{4-9,11,12}

The origin of the enhanced GMI effect of amorphous wires is discussed in terms of high circumferential magnetic permeability, μ_ϕ , together with strong magnetic field, H , dependence of μ_ϕ . Usually GMI effect is represented in terms of the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$,^{6,8,9} defined as

$$\Delta Z/Z = [Z(H) - Z(H_{max})]/Z(H_{max}) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where Z is the sample impedance and H_{max} is the maximum applied magnetic field (typically below a few kA/m).

Different fabrication techniques allow fabrication of amorphous wires with diameters from 0.1 to 150 μm .^{4-9,11,12} The most extended diameters range can be achieved by using Taylor-Ulitovsky

method allowing fabrication of amorphous microwires with diameters from 0.1 to 100 μm covered by thin glass-coating.^{11–14} Excellent magnetic softness along with high GMI effect and excellent mechanical properties in glass-coated amorphous microwires have been reported.^{4,11,12} On the other hand, the glass coating provides several functionalities for emerging application owing to better corrosion properties or biocompatibility.^{12–15} Therefore, studies of magnetic properties and GMI in glass-coated microwires have attracted special attention along the last years.^{11–20}

From the viewpoint of applications in magnetic sensors and smart composites applications, development of glass-coated microwires with high $\Delta Z/Z$ - value is essentially relevant. Therefore, considerable attention has been paid to GMI effect tuning in glass-coated microwires.^{11,12}

Consequently, in this paper we provide our latest attempt on optimization of the magnetic softness and GMI effect in Co-rich glass-coated magnetic microwires.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

We studied magnetic properties and GMI effect in amorphous $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated amorphous microwires with metallic nucleus diameters, d , of about 40 μm and a total diameter, D , of about 45 μm (sample 1) and $d \approx 25.8 \mu\text{m}$ $D \approx 29.2 \mu\text{m}$ manufactured by the aforementioned Taylor-Ulitovsky method.^{12,16,21}

Briefly, the preparation method (known as the Taylor-Ulitovsky method) consists of melting a metallic alloy inside a Duran-type glass tube using a high-frequency inductor, forming the glass capillary, drawing of such capillary filled with the molten metallic alloy surrounded by a softened glass, and winding of the solidified glass-coated microwires onto a rotating bobbin.^{12,16,21} In fact, this fabrication technique is known since the 60s,^{12,16} however it was considerably modified during the last years.^{12,16,21}

The chemical composition was selected considering dependence of the magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , in Co-Fe based amorphous alloys and vanishing λ_s -values ($\lambda_s \approx 10^{-7}$) in Co-rich.^{22,23}

Axial hysteresis loops were measured using specially designed setup utilizing the fluxmetric method, developed for studies of soft magnetic microwires with reduced diameters.²⁴ In this setup the electromotive force, ϵ , induced in the pick-up coil by the change of magnetic flux, ϕ , by the remagnetization of the sample with magnetization, M , is measured. This remagnetization is produced under the effect of the applied magnetic field, H , and ϵ , is given as

$$\epsilon = -N \frac{d\phi}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where N - is a number of turns of the pick-up coil. The use of the compensation coil allows to eliminate the magnetic flux component originated by the applied magnetic field itself. In numerous previous studies this experimental setup was successfully used for measurements of the hysteresis loops of extremely soft magnetic microwires allowing mA/m coercivity, H_c , resolution.^{12,24} For better comparison of the samples with different diameter, the hysteresis loops were represented as the normalized magnetization M/M_0 (where M_0 is the magnetic moment of the samples at maximum magnetic field amplitude, H_0) versus H .

FIG. 1. Hysteresis loops of the sample 1 (a) and sample 2(b).

The GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, was defined using (1) from the $Z(H)$ dependence measured using a vector network analyzer. The Z -value is obtained from the reflection coefficient, S_{11} . Use of the specially designed sample holder with coaxial line connections allows to measure $Z(H)$ dependencies up to GHz frequencies.²⁵

The amorphous state studied sample has been confirmed by a broad halo in the x-ray spectra obtained using x-ray diffraction.

The samples have been annealed in a conventional furnace (Thermolyne 62700) at temperatures, T_{ann} , up to 300°C for 60 min. The insulating and continuous glass-coating allows annealing of studied glass-coated microwires to be annealed in air.

A recently developed setup²³ designed to evaluate the λ_s of magnetic microwires using the so-called Small Angle Magnetization Rotation (SAMR) method²⁶ was used for λ_s measurements.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hysteresis loop of both studied samples are shown in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1, rather soft magnetic properties of both studied microwire with coercivity, H_c , about 21 A/m (sample 1) and $H_c \approx 23$ A/m (sample 2) and magnetic anisotropy field, H_k , about 130 A/m (sample 1) and 150 A/m (sample 2) are evidenced. Such magnetic properties are typical for amorphous microwires with low negative λ_s -values.

As shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), a rather high maximum GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z_m$, above 550% is observed in both as-prepared samples being even above 600% in sample 2. A double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies, typical for magnetic wires with circumferential magnetic anisotropy, are observed at all measured frequencies in both studied samples (see Fig. 2). Such features of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies correlate with the hysteresis loop, particularly with low H_c and H_k -values.

The aforementioned $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed at each frequency, f . However, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are affected by f , being higher at

FIG. 2. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at different frequencies in sample 1 (a) and sample 2 (b).

FIG. 3. $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependencies evaluated from $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies for both studied samples.

$f \geq 200$ MHz. The $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependencies obtained from $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured in the frequency range up to 800 MHz are shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen from Fig. 3, slightly higher $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are obtained for sample 1 at $f < 100$ MHz. However, higher $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed for sample 2 at $f \geq 100$ MHz.

As previously already discussed, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ ratio in magnetic wires usually exhibits maximum value at some optimum frequency, f_o .^{24,25} The $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value and the frequency, f_o , at which $\Delta Z/Z_m$ is observed are related with wire diameter and with magnetoelastic anisotropy.^{24,25,27} Thus, a decrease in magnetic wire diameter is associated with an increase in the f_o -value.²⁷

The $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values obtained for the sample 2 ($\Delta Z/Z_m \approx 625\%$) are among the highest reported for as-prepared glass-coated

FIG. 4. Hysteresis loops of as-prepared (a) and annealed at $T_{ann} = 300^\circ\text{C}$ (b) sample 1.

microwires.^{11,12,28} However, early was shown that appropriate annealing usually allows further $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value improvement.^{11,12}

Therefore, we studied the magnetic properties and GMI effect in sample 1 annealed at 300°C . After such annealing, we observed a change in the hysteresis loops, which consists of a decrease in the value of H_k -value up to $H_k \approx 75$ A/m, and an increase in the remanent magnetization, M_r/M_s , while H_c remains practically unchanged ($H_c \approx 24$ A/m, see Figs. 4(a) and 4(b)). Similar changes in hysteresis loops towards perfectly rectangular after annealing have previously been reported in various Co-rich microwires with thinner diameters.^{24,29} One of the reasons for such change in hysteresis loops was a change in λ_s value and even sign after annealing attributed to the relaxation of the internal stresses.²⁹ The experimental results obtained by the SAMR method confirm the change in λ_s from low negative ($\lambda_s \approx -0.9 \times 10^{-6}$) to low positive ($\lambda_s \approx 0.7 \times 10^{-6}$) after annealing.

Additionally, a substantial increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ up to about 735% is observed after annealing at 300°C (see Figs. 5(c) and 5(d)).

The observed change in the hysteresis loop shape, in $\Delta Z/Z$ -value and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence upon annealing must be attributed to change in λ_s and corresponding change of domain structure of studied microwires after annealing. From the core-shell domain structure model (confirmed experimentally by direct domain structure observation using the Magneto-Optical Kerr Effect, MOKE or by the Magneto-Optical Indicator Film, MOIF, methods)²⁹⁻³² the inner axially magnetized core radius, R_c , is related with the remanent magnetization, M_r/M_s ,³³ as

$$R_c = R(M_r/M_s)^{1/2}, \quad (3)$$

FIG. 5. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared and annealed sample 1 measured at 80 MHz (a), 100 MHz (b) and 200 MHz (c) and (d) $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ of as-prepared and annealed sample 1.

where R is the microwire radius. From (3) we must suggest a substantial R_c increase from $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $16 \mu\text{m}$ upon annealing (considering change of M_r/M_s 0.15 to 0.89). Recently, change of hysteresis loops from inclined to rectangular was reported after annealing of studied sample 1 at temperatures between 275 and 350°C .³⁴

It is worth noting that the $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependencies of as-prepared and annealed sample 1 are rather different. Thus, an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ after annealing is produced at a relatively low f ($f \leq 250$ MHz): superior $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values in annealed sample 1 are obtained at $10 \leq f \leq 250$ MHz. Additionally, in annealed sample 1 $f_0 \approx 80$ MHz, while in as-prepared sample $f_0 \approx 200$ MHz (see Fig. 5(d)). One of the reasons of such change in the $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependence after annealing can be related with aforementioned change in the domain structure. Relatively low M_r/M_s -value points out to transverse character of magnetic anisotropy (and low R_c value) and hence main contribution of magnetization rotation in axial magnetization rotation process. While, higher M_r/M_s -value or annealed sample 1 must be attributed to change of magnetic anisotropy towards axial. The domain wall propagation is involved in axial magnetization process of magnetic wires with axial magnetic anisotropy. However, at elevated frequencies domain walls are damped,⁸ that

may affect the GMI effect in magnetic wires with axial magnetic anisotropy.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The GMI effect and the magnetic properties of $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated microwires with two different diameter of metallic nucleus were studied. Substantial difference in frequency dependencies of GMI effect for studied samples are observed. A remarkable improvement of up to 735% in GMI ration is observed after annealing of the thicker microwire under appropriate conditions. The observed change in magnetic properties and improvement of the GMI coefficient are discussed taking into account the relaxation of internal stresses, as well as the change in the sign and values of the magnetostriction coefficient after annealing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by EU under “INFINITE” (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01-06) project and “Harmony” (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01) projects, by the Spanish MICIN, under PID2022-141373NB-I00 project, by the Government of the Basque Country under Elkartek (MOSINCO and ATLANTIS) projects and under the scheme of “Ayuda a Grupos Consolidados” (ref. IT1670-22). The authors thank the technical and human support provided by SGIker of UPV/EHU (Medidas Magneticas Gipuzkoa) and European funding (ERDF and ESF). J.O. thanks the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology (MESCYT) of the Dominican Republic.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

A. Gonzalez: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **P. Corte-León:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **V. Zhukova:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal). **J. M. Blanco:** Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **J. Olivera:** Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal). **A. Zhukov:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- ¹G. Herzer, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **254**, 598 (2003).
- ²F. Fiorillo, G. Bertotti, C. Appino, and M. Pasquale, "Soft magnetic materials," in *Wiley Encyclopedia of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, edited by J. Webster (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Torino, Italy, 1999), p. 42.
- ³M. Hagiwara, A. Inoue, and T. Masumoto, *Metall. Trans. A* **13**, 373 (1982).
- ⁴T. Goto, M. Nagano, and N. Wehara, *Trans. Jpn. Inst. Met.* **18**, 759 (1977).
- ⁵K. Mohri, F. B. Humphrey, K. Kawashima, K. Kimura, and M. Mizutani, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **26**, 1789 (1990).
- ⁶A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, P. Corte-León, L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, J. M. Blanco, and V. Zhukova, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **498**, 166180 (2020).
- ⁷P. Rudkowski, G. Rudkowska, and J. O. Strom-Olsen, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: A* **133**, 158–161 (1991).
- ⁸M. Knobel, M. Vazquez, and L. Kraus, *Handbook of Magnetic Materials* (2003), Vol. 15, p. 497.
- ⁹K. Mohri, T. Uchiyama, L. P. Shen, C. M. Cai, and L. V. Panina, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **249**, 351 (2002).
- ¹⁰A. P. Zhukov, *Mater. Des.* **14**(5), 299 (1993).
- ¹¹K. R. Pirota, L. Kraus, H. Chiriac, and M. Knobel, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **221**, L243 (2000).
- ¹²A. Zhukov, P. Corte-Leon, L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, A. Gonzalez, and V. Zhukova, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **55**, 253003 (2022).
- ¹³H. Chiriac, N. Lupu, G. Stoian, G. Ababei, S. Corodeanu, and T.-A. Óvári, *Crystals* **7**, 48 (2017).
- ¹⁴P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, J. González, M. Churyukanova, S. Taskaev, and A. Zhukov, *J. Alloys Compd.* **831**, 150992 (2020).
- ¹⁵D. Kozejova, L. Fecova, P. Klein, R. Sabol, R. Hudak, I. Sulla, D. Mudronova, J. Galik, and R. Varga, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **470**, 2 (2019).
- ¹⁶S. A. Baranov, V. S. Larin, and A. V. Torcunov, *Crystals* **7**, 136 (2017).
- ¹⁷O. Mitxelena-Iribarren, J. Campisi, I. Martínez de Apellániz, S. Lizarbe-Sancha, S. Arana, V. Zhukova, M. Mujika, and A. Zhukov, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C* **106**, 110261 (2020).
- ¹⁸M. Ipatov, G. R. Aranda, V. Zhukova, L. V. Panina, J. González, and A. Zhukov, *Appl. Phys. A* **103**(3), 693 (2011).
- ¹⁹V. Zhukova, A. F. Cobeño, A. Zhukov, A. R. de Arellano Lopez, S. López-Pombero, J. M. Blanco, V. Larin, and J. Gonzalez, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **249**, 79 (2002).
- ²⁰M. Vázquez, A. Zhukov, P. Aragonese, J. Arcas, J. Garcia-Beneytez, P. Maria, and A. Hernando, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **34**(3), 724 (1998).
- ²¹T.-A. Óvári, N. Lupu, and H. Chiriac, *Rapidly Solidified Magnetic Nanowires and Submicron Wires in Advanced Magnetic Materials* (Intech Open Access Publisher, Rijeka, Croatia, 2012), pp. 1–32.
- ²²Y. Konno and K. Mohri, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **25**, 3623 (1989).
- ²³M. Churyukanova, V. Semenkova, S. Kaloshkin, E. Shuvaeva, S. Gudoshnikov, V. Zhukova, I. Shchetinin, and A. Zhukov, *Phys. Status Solidi A* **213**(2), 363 (2016).
- ²⁴L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, J. Gonzalez, and A. Zhukov, *Sensors* **20**, 1558 (2020).
- ²⁵A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, P. Corte-Leon, J. M. Blanco, L. González-Legarreta, and V. Zhukova, *IEEE Instrum. Meas. Mag.* **23**(1), 56 (2020).
- ²⁶K. Narita, J. Yamasaki, and H. Fukunaga, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **16**(2), 435 (1980).
- ²⁷D. Ménard, M. Britel, P. Ciureanu, and A. Yelon, *J. Appl. Phys.* **84**(5), 2805 (1998).
- ²⁸A. Zhukov, V. Zhukova, J. M. Blanco, and J. Gonzalez, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **294**, 182 (2005).
- ²⁹A. Zhukov, A. Talaat, M. Churyukanova, S. Kaloshkin, V. Semenkova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, and V. Zhukova, *J. Alloys Compd.* **664**, 235 (2016); J. N. Nderu, M. Takajo, J. Yamasaki, and F. B. Humphrey, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **34**, 1312 (1998).
- ³⁰O. I. Aksenov and A. S. Aronin, *Phys. Solid State* **63**(4), 513 (2021).
- ³¹N. N. Orlova, A. S. Aronin, S. I. Bozhko, Y. P. Kabanov, and V. S. Gornakov, *J. Appl. Phys.* **111**, 073906 (2012).
- ³²V. Zhukova, J. M. Blanco, A. Chizhik, M. Ipatov, and A. Zhukov, *Front. Phys.* **13**(2), 137501 (2018).
- ³³M. Vázquez and D.-X. Chen, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **31**, 1229 (1995).
- ³⁴P. Corte-León, A. Gonzalez, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, and A. Zhukov, *J. Alloys Compd.* **999**, 175023 (2024).